

Case Study: Linking Career Education to University Education in Japan

Authors : Kumiko Inagaki

Abstract : Japanese society is experiencing an aging population and declining birth rate along with the popularization of higher education, spread of economic globalization, rapid progress in technical innovation, changes in employment conditions, and emergence of a knowledge-based society. Against this background, interest in career education at Japanese universities has increased in recent years. This paper describes how the government has implemented career education policies in Japan, and introduces the cases of two universities that have successfully linked career education to university education in Japan.

Keywords : career education, employability, higher education, japanese university, university education

Conference Title : ICES 2014 : International Conference on Educational Sciences

Conference Location : Amsterdam, The Netherlands

Conference Dates : August 07-08, 2014